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**ANALYSIS OF GROUND SEGMENT BROADCAST ARCHITECTURES FOR THE
WIDEBAND GAPFILLER SATELLITE (WGS)**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to summarize the findings of an assessment tasked by the Joint Staff regarding the broadcast ground segment architecture for the Wideband Gapfiller Satellite (WGS). Broadcast services within the DoD are currently being fulfilled by the Global Broadcast Service (GBS) with Ka-band packages on three UHF Follow-On (UFO) satellites. On UFO, GBS operates at Ka-band with up to four 24 Mbps uplinks injected at 30-GHz and 1-meter receive suites at 20-GHz. WGS will provide a broadcast capability that can emulate the GBS capability on the UFO satellites. However, unlike UFO, WGS has the capability to permit GBS injection at either Ka-band (30 GHz) or X-band (8-GHz), and be cross-banded and received by current GBS receive-only suites at 20-GHz. Original plans were to buy three new GBS Ka-band injection terminals to support GBS on WGS; however, to save costs, one alternative is to use existing DSCS X-band terminals to perform the GBS injection on WGS with crossbanding to the current Ka-band GBS receive suites. Then, as UFO GBS satellites reach their end of life, the existing Ka-band GBS injection terminals will replace the X-band injection, freeing the latter for other missions. This paper examines various options and provides recommendations for GBS injection on WGS in consideration of the available X- and Ka-band bandwidth and the corresponding antenna coverage issues. This paper also discusses an option for GBS reception at X-band for sites with existing X-band two-way services. Based on this capability, the paper shows options for a Ka-only GBS, cross-banded Ka-to-X band GBS, X-to-Ka-band GBS, and X- to X-band GBS. Planned use of these options will provide coverage flexibility and ease the current planning burden and will minimize the amount of beam movement to achieve desired worldwide coverage goals.

OVERVIEW

The WGS is being designed to satisfy a number of key wideband mission and communication requirements. The scenarios used in the investigation are derived from requirements identified in two databases: the Integrated Communications Data Base (ICDB) and the Emerging Requirements Data Base (ERDB), Version 5.1, Rev. 2 (as of January 1999) currently referred to as the Satellite Data Base (SDB). This database is a comprehensive catalog of near and far-term requirements for SATCOM services submitted by CINCs, Services, and Agencies (C/S/A) to the Joint Staff. To obtain a realistic measure of DoD's communications requirements in an operational environment, the SDB is used to quantify the needs of users during specific deployment scenarios. The scenarios are based on current Defense Planning Guidance (DPG) for the 2004 – 2010 period. The scenarios are based on a two-theater war {combined major theater of war, (CMTW)}.

Due to the significant increase in requirements projected for WGS, the majority of the scenario requirements are based on the SDB (Version 5.1, Rev.2). As indicated previously, the SDB contains generalized tactical (and non-tactical) user requirements that must be tailored to a given user deployment scenario that depends on a specific tactical situation. The tailoring of these requirements is for a specific scenario (e.g., combined major theater of war (CMTW) for a two-theater of war scenario).

Broadcast services within the DoD are being fulfilled by the Global Broadcast Service (GBS). WGS will provide a similar capability to that currently being used on the UFO satellites. To accomplish this mission, a broadcast injection path must be established to the WGS satellites. Initial concepts required that three new Primary Injection

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Points (PIP) be deployed at or near the existing Satellite Broadcast Manager (SBM) locations. Based upon discussions within the community, the Joint Staff requested examination of possible options to provide the WGS injection path.

REQUIREMENTS AND ASSUMPTIONS

The following assumptions were used to conduct the analysis.

- GBS requirements as stated in the SDB with four simultaneous links from the PIP locations
- Connectivity from WGS hubs is via X- or Ka-band
- Teleport type hubs are connected via DISN back via 60-ft and 38 ft X-band or 8.1 m Ka-band earth terminals

WGS satellite performance parameters as outlined in Tables 1-4 were used for the analysis.

Table 1. X-Band Shapeable Antenna (SCA)G/T

Beam Diameter (Circular Coverage)	Scan Angle			
	0°	4°	6°	8.7°
2.22°	6.2	5.6	5.2	5.0
4.00°	2.3	2.0	1.8	2.1
6.00°	-0.6	-0.8	-0.9	-0.6
8.00°	-2.9	-3.0	-2.9	-2.7

Table 2. Ka-Band G/T

Antenna	G/T	Description
NCA's 1 - 6	8.4 dB/K	1.51° circular coverage
ACA 1	-1.0 dB/K	4.49° circular coverage
ACA 2	-1.4 dB/K	4.49° circular coverage
NCA's 7 - 8	7.4 dB/K	1.51° circular coverage
ECR	-10.5 dB/K	17.4 circular coverage

Table 3. Ka-Band EIRP

Antenna	Operating Point EIRP	Noise Power Ratio	Description
NCA 1, 2, 3	58.1 dBW	≥16.5 dB	1.51° circular coverage
NCA 4, 5, 6	55.2 dBW	≥16.5 dB	1.51° circular coverage
ACA 1	42.6 dBW	≥16.5 dB	4.49° circular coverage
ACA 2	42.4 dBW	≥16.5 dB	4.49° circular coverage
NCA 7,8	57.6 dBW	≥16.5 dB	1.51° circular coverage
ECX	34.3 dBW	≥16.5 dB	17.4 circular coverage

Table 5 contains the assumed parameters for the WGS ground segment.

Table 4. X-Band EIRP

Beam Diameter (Circular Coverage)	Scan Angle			
	0°	4°	6°	8.7°
2.22°	60.8	60.2	59.8	59.2
4.00°	55.7	55.7	55.4	55.1
6.00°	53.4	53.3	53.0	52.5
8.00°	51.6	51.0	50.7	50.7

Table 5. Ground Segment Parameters

Terminal Nomenclature	Ant Size	f	Tx/Rx	EIRP (dBW) (Lin/Sat)	G/T (dB/K)
AN/FSC-78	60'	X	Tx/Rx	91/97	39
AN/GSC-39	38'	X	Tx/Rx	87/93	34
AN/GSC-39	38'	X	Tx/Rx	87/93	34
AN/GSC-52 Mod	38'	X	Tx/Rx	87/93	34
Large Fixed Ka	8.1m	Ka	Tx/Rx	84 / 90	33.8
GBS PIP	8.1m	Ka	Tx	81/85	N/A
GBS TIP	2.4m	Ka	Tx	75.2	N/A
GBS FGRT	1.0m	Ka	Rx	N/A	19
GBS TGRT	1.0m	Ka	Rx	N/A	19

Analysis Section

This section will discuss the user requirements, technical considerations, operational impacts, and alternative architectures.

With WGS having a digital filter, switching, and routing capability (FS&R) (which is also called the channelizer), the existing GBS frequency plan can be emulated. Figure 1 shows this capability. Therefore, injection and reception on the WGS could be accomplished in the same manner as UFO. Uplinks from the PIP and transmission to the receive suites could be at Ka. Figure 2 shows the introduction of a cross-banding concept for WGS/GBS services. The concept is to use the uplink injection at either Ka (30 GHz) or X (8GHz), with multi-cast and cross-band to X and Ka on the downlinks using the flexible transponder F S&R function. Hence, ships or other users in a broad coverage area (2,400 mile diameter spot at subsatellite and larger areas off the subsatellite point) can receive GBS signals at X-Band.

- Equivalent capability as UFO
- Per satellite
 - 4 uplinks from fixed injection site
 - 1 Uplink from Tactical injection

Figure 1. WGS Frequency Plan For GBS

This avoids or at least minimizes any potential antenna coverage conflicts between ships not in the immediate theater and tactical users in a 2-way Ka-band service area. (Earth terminal impacts for reception of GBS reception at X-band include the need for a simple X- to L-band converter.) Note that the current GBS downlink Ka-band transmissions are LHCP, oppositely polarized to the Milstar and UFO 20-GHz RHCP downlinks. This concept maintains the current polarization of the GBS downlink and also utilizes RHCP GBS injection. It is assumed that the 2-way Ka Gapfiller operation would be selectable for either polarization transmission option. For the uplink, existing X band facilities could also be used. Another option is the sharing of the large 2-way Ka terminals for both teleport and broadcast. Since the WGS has very high uplink gains from the Shaped Beam Antennas (SBA) at X band and Narrow Coverage Antenna (NCA) at Ka band, it is deemed feasible to share either existing DSCS or large 2-way Ka for injection. Additionally, with spatial frequency reuse at both X and Ka band, bandwidth is deemed available for GBS injection. The following section will address three options for the injection on WGS.

Figure 2. WGS Broadcast and Multicast Concept

DESCRIPTION OF OPTIONS

Option 1 Separate PIP's for WGS

This option would deploy 3 separate PIP's for WGS. A total of 9 large Ka earth terminals compose this option. WGS PIP's would be located at existing GBS injection sites and 6 large Ka terminals are available for tactical reachback at Teleport locations. The following analysis assumes equivalent capacity as the current UFO. The necessary PIP EIRP for Option 1 is 70 dBW in clear sky. To meet the required availability in rain, the total EIRP requirement is 83 dBW. This is sufficient to satisfy 3 links at 23 Mbps and 1 link at 6 Mbps. Figure 3 shows the possible amplifier and antenna size options to meet the required EIRP. As can be seen, WGS with high gain

Figure 3. Option 1 PIP-HPA/Antenna Alternatives

uplink beams at Ka band allows the potential for smaller antennas at the PIP location. The disadvantage of this option is the cost of a separate terminal for injection (9 total terminals).

Option 2 Combined PIP and 2-Way Ka

This option uses one antenna and terminal combination to satisfy the GBS and 2-Way Ka reachback requirements. In this option a total of six terminals are procured. Three are located at the existing PIP locations and are used for both 2-Way reachback and GBS injection. The remaining three

Figure 4. Option 2 Terminal EIRP Required for GBS and Teleport (Combined PIP and 2-Way Ka)

Figure 5. HPA Requirements for Option 2

are located at Teleport locations. Figure 4 displays the total EIRP requirements for a combined approach. Analysis of the antenna size to support a combined approach indicates that either a 5.7m or 8.1m can support the total EIRP. Figure 5 outlines the analysis results. Advantages for this option include a reduction of the total number of terminals required.

Option 3 X-Band Injection

This option uses the existing X-band terminals at or in the proximity of the current PIP locations. Modification to the existing X-band terminals to include the GBS injection equipment would be necessary. An initial impact estimate

of required equipment rack space concluded that the modification could be accomplished. A review of this conclusion and a site survey should be accomplished to validate the conclusions. The six large fixed Ka terminals would be located at Teleport sites for reachback services. X-Band EIRP requirements are approximately 25 watts for an AN/GSC-52 and 11 watts for an AN/FSC-78. Since these large X-band terminals are designed for many hundreds of watts of HPA power, EIRP is not an issue for injection. A key advantage in this option is that if the WGS does not deliver three satellites to orbit, the investment in GBS injection is minimized. Additionally, GBS injection at X-band can support higher link availability especially for the Atlantic region since the elevation angles to the 12° West satellite are approximately 9°. A potential issue is available X band bandwidth at these sites. The following section will address this issue.

The WGS is being designed to take advantage of frequency reuse using spatial techniques. These techniques have been used extensively in the commercial satellite environment for years. At X-Band, the WGS will be able to generate eight independent beams. Since these beams can be pointed at different geographic areas, the X-Band frequency can be reused. The maximum X to Ka bandwidth available on WGS which can be assigned to these eight beams is approximately 1750 MHz. Broadcast functions would require less than 10% of this bandwidth. However, the issue of reuse must be examined and the CMTW scenario will be used in the analysis. First we will examine the bandwidth use from a satellite perspective by investigating the bandwidth available on the coverage beams close to the injection site (Sigonella, Northwest, and Hawaii). This will include all requirements assigned to the scenario (tactical, reachback, and fixed) Second, we will account for the bandwidth used for Teleport tactical reachback and for fixed infrastructure (DISN) at specific sites of interest. The CMTW is a very stressing capacity and coverage scenario. More typical operations are less stressing. Figure 6¹ shows the Indian Ocean coverages for an SWA MTW and the possible beams that could impact the frequency reuse.

The areas in red show the potential impacts for bandwidth at the PIP in Sigonella. Beams DCA1 and 2 and MCA 4 are the beams carrying traffic in the Sigonella area. The total uplink bandwidth of these adjacent beams is 340 MHz. This leaves 160 MHz for GBS injection from Italy into IO WGS. The bandwidth requirement for broadcast

¹ Note that the Medium Coverage Area (MCA) and the Dispersed Coverage Area (DCA) are now called Shaped Coverage Area (SCA).

is approximately 120 MHz. Additionally, the SWA scenario was developed for the WGS source selection process and the majority of requirements were assigned to the IO region. If X-band bandwidth at Sigonella became an issue, requirements could be potentially reassigned to the East Atlantic WGS satellite (see Figure 7). The

Figure 6. SWA MTW Coverages

Teleport capacity requirements at Lago which is in the same coverage area as Sigonella are 59 Mbps and will require

Figure 7. Atlantic SWA Coverages

approximately 48 MHz. Fixed traffic requires approximately 50.7 Mbps. This requires 40 MHz using rate 2/3 8PSK. Additionally we must account for potentially 50 MHz of bandwidth assigned to the earth coverage antenna. This summarizes as a total bandwidth of 140 MHz and permits 360 MHz to be assigned to tactical requirements. As seen previously, when taking into account tactical to tactical needs, 160 MHz remains for injection. Therefore, sufficient bandwidth is available for X-band injection at Sigonella from a satellite perspective. Injection at the Northwest site can be accommodated since a high-gain uplink beam (MCA 1) is

placed on the area as shown in Figure 7. 134 Mbps have been identified for the MCA 1 beam. This will require approximately 107 MHz, and therefore more than 300 MHz would be available for GBS injection. For the remaining MTW, Figure 8 shows the coverage for the NEA. Hawaii is covered by a high gain beam, MCA 4. Since no other coverage areas are close to MCA 4, spatial reuse is feasible. Teleport requires 93 MHz. There are fixed requirements for uplink bandwidth in Hawaii of 30 Mbps (24 MHz). When adding the 50-MHz earth coverage, the total becomes 117 MHz. This leaves more than 300 MHz for GBS injection from Hawaii into WPAC WGS.

Figure 8. NEA Coverages

WGS Ground Segment Broadcast Summary

This report has examined three options for the GBS injection services on the WGS. The options are:

1. Separate PIP's for WGS
2. Combined PIP's and 2-Way Ka Teleport Terminals
3. Use of existing X-band terminal for PIP's.

Each of the options is technically feasible. From an overall investment viewpoint, option 3 has the lowest life cycle cost and provides the most flexibility. A review of the total bandwidth requirements in a CMTW scenario has shown that there will be sufficient X-band bandwidth to implement option 3.

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